

THE IMPACT OF WOMEN SELF HELP GROUP ON THE LIVING CONDITION OF RURAL POOR IN RURAL ECONOMY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to enumerate the impact of the Women Self Help Group on the living conditions of the rural poor in the Tirunelveli District, based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data connecting to the study was collected with the help of the specially prepared Interview Schedule. The data were collected from a significant Women Self Help Group sample from the Tirunelveli district. Stratified Proportionate sampling techniques methods were used. 200 sample women's self-help groups were selected for the study. The secondary data was collected from Journals, Books, Reports, Newspapers, and the like to substantiate the study and as supportive evidence in the field of study. Based on the evaluation carried out at the field level, it can be inferred that women's self-help group holds the key to the development of the country's vast rural population. It is deemed to have huge potential in empowering rural communities. The self-help group is capable of enhancing the income level, food security, and livelihood security of the Women Self-help group sustainably. Women's self-help groups brought very positive changes in respect of employment, income, self-confidence, and security. It boosted the village economy and was found beneficial to the rural poor.

KEYWORDS: Rural Economy, Rural Poor, Living Condition, and Impact

INTRODUCTION

Rural women in India constitute a significant portion of the total population of the country and their backwardness is one of the major handicaps in the path of the country's development. In the rural society characterized by deep-rooted, age-old sex discrimination, economic oppression, and social stratification women have engaged in a place much below the men. Not only in Indian society. The inferior position of women can be seen in all the countries particularly third world countries which is social. Economically backward, seen in all the

countries but the degree of subordination varies according to the level of development on the one hand and the ownership of means of production on the other.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Improvement in the standard of living of rural poor, especially of Women Self-help groups in developing countries like India is a global challenge. The World Bank estimates show that 80 percent of India's population lives below the international poverty line of Rs.2 per day (2005). India is on the list of 94 countries on the poverty line. Based on June 2010 data, 859 lakh families were living below the poverty line in India. The labor force will increase by 520 lakh during the 11th plan period based on the growth of the working-age population.

Job-seeking women in rural areas will be around 650 lakhs. This increase will be in addition to the current 350 lakhs unemployed. So, India has to employ around 1000 lakh people most of them in rural areas. According to the Planning Commission assessment, India cannot provide full employment but may approach to generate 650 lakhs of employment, to bring down the unemployment rate. In this perspective, the parliament has enacted various entrepreneurship schemes, especially for women Undoubtedly this is the largest ever public employment opportunity visualized in human history. The essence of the Act is "to provide for the enhancement of livelihood security of the women's self-help group

In the state of Tamilnadu, women's help group contribution of women is more in the other scheme, The researcher has interested in investigating the socio-economic development of women as a part of upliftment and so the topic of research is named "Impact of Women Self Help Group on the living condition of rural poor in Tirunelveli district".

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- **To examine the impact of the Women Self Help group on the living conditions of the rural poor in Tirunelveli district.**
- **To identify the problems faced by rural poor Women's self-help groups.**

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to enumerate the impact of the Women's Self-help group on the living conditions of the rural poor in the Tirunelveli district, based on both the primary and secondary data. The primary data relating to the study was collected with the help of the specially prepared Interview Schedule. The data were collected from a considerable sample of Women Self-help groups from the Tirunelveli district. Stratified Proportionate sampling

techniques methods were used. 200 samples rural poor were selected for the study. The secondary data was collected from Journals, Books, Reports, Newspapers, and the like to substantiate the study and as supportive pieces of evidence in the field of study.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Impact of Women entrepreneurs on the living condition and the age group of respondents

To find out the significant difference in the impact of Women's Self-help groups on the living conditions among the rural poor of different age groups, ANOVA was attempted with the null hypothesis as **there is no significant difference in the impact of women's Self-help groups on the living condition among the different age group of rural poor in Tirunelveli district.** The resulting mean score among the rural poor of different age groups on the status and the respective „F“ statistics are presented in Table 1.

Table - 1
Impact of Women Self Help Group on the living condition and the age group of respondents in Tirunelveli district

Sl. No	Impact of Women Self Help Group on the living condition	Age Group (Mean Score among the Respondents)				F Statistics
		Less than 25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	
1.	Sustainable changes in own lives	3.4345	3.1429	3.2182	3.0417	2.246
2.	Improvement in consumption level	3.4048	3.2500	3.1091	3.9167	2.330
3.	Savings	3.4286	3.2857	3.3455	2.8750	1.855
4..	Enhancement of self-confidence	3.2024	3.4643	3.0727	3.1667	1.086
5.	Contribution to food security	3.0476	3.1429	3.7455	3.0417	1.467
6.	Health care contribution	3.0958	3.1071	3.8364	3.0000	1.015
7.	Repayment of debts	3.0833	3.1045	3.0909	3.0417	0.021
8.	Contribution to their family expenses	3.5000	3.7143	3.7273	3.1667	2.602*
9.	Participation in income creation	3.2202	3.1786	3.2364	3.0000	0.440
10..	Decision-making skills	3.3333	3.3214	3.5273	3.0417	1.226
11.	Economic independence	3.3214	2.9286	3.2727	3.2500	1.029
12.	Earning opportunities	3.3810	3.1071	3.3636	3.4583	0.524
13.	Contribution to household income	3.3452	3.6786	3.0182	3.0417	4.000*

Source: Primary data

*Significant at five per cent level

Table 1 shows the mean score of the impact of the Women Self help group on the living condition among the different age groups of rural poor along with its respective „F“ statistics. The important impact of the Self-help group on the living condition among the rural poor who are in the age group of fewer than 25 years are contributing to their family expenditure and contribution to household income and their respective mean scores are 3.5000 and, 3.3452 among the rural poor who are in the age group of 26-35 years, contribution to their family expenditure and sustainable changes in own lives and their respective mean scores are 3.7143 and 3.4345. The important impact of Self-help groups on the living condition among the rural poor who are in the age group of 36-45 years is health care contribution and contribution to food security and their respective mean scores are 3.8364 and 3.7455, among the rural poor who are in the age group of above 45 years, improvement in consumption level and earning opportunities and their respective mean scores are 3.9167 and 3.4583. Regarding the impact of Self-help groups on the living condition, the significant difference among the different age groups of rural poor, are identified in the case of contribution to their family expenditure and contribution to household income, since the respective „F“ statistics are significant at 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Impact of Self help group on the living condition and the religious group of respondents

To find out the significant difference in the impact of Self-help groups on the living condition among the rural poor of different religious groups, ANOVA was attempted with the null hypothesis as **there is no significant difference in the impact of women Self-help Group on the living condition and the religious group of rural poor in Tirunelveli district.** The resulted mean score among the rural poor of different religious groups on the status and the respective „F“ statistics are presented in Table 2.

Table - 2

Impact of Women Self Help Group on the living condition and the religious group of respondents in Tirunelveli district

Sl. No	Impact of Women Self Help Group on the living condition	Religion (Mean Score among the Respondents)			F Statistics
		Hindu	Muslim	Christian	
1.	Sustainable changes in own lives	3.3758	3.2152	3.1579	1.432
2.	Improvement in consumption level	3.3989	3.0253	3.3684	3.614*

3.	Savings	3.4633	3.0886	3.3692	3.274*
4.	Enhancement of self-confidence	3.2260	3.0506	3.5786	2.641*
5.	Contribution to food security	3.0678	2.7089	3.5263	6.379*
6.	Health care contribution	3.1028	2.8101	3.3684	3.615*
7.	Repayment of debts	3.0791	2.7266	2.9474	0.268
8.	Contribution to their family expenditure	3.5028	3.6076	3.5789	0.378
9.	Participation in income generation	3.2260	3.1266	3.2632	0.368
10.	Decision-making skills	3.2994	3.4684	3.2798	0.763
11.	Economic independence	3.3220	3.2025	3.0000	0.921
12.	Earning opportunities	3.3955	3.3544	3.1527	1.013
13.	Contribution to household income	3.3390	2.9620	2.8944	4.435*

Source: Primary data

*Significant at five per cent level

Table 2 shows the mean score of the impact of the Women Self Help Group on the living conditions among the different religious groups of rural poor along with its respective „F“ statistics. The important impact of the women's self-help group on the living condition among the rural poor who belong to Hindus is a contribution to their family expenditure and savings and their respective mean scores are 3.5028 and 3.4633, among the rural poor who belong to Christian contribution to their family expenditure and enhancement of self-confidence and their respective mean scores are 3.5789 and 3.5786. The important impact of the women's self-help group on the living conditions among the rural poor who belong to Muslims is a contribution to their family expenditure and decision-making skills and their respective mean scores are 3.6076 and 3.4684. Regarding the impact of women's self-help groups on the living conditions, the significant differences among the different religious groups of rural poor, are identified in the case of contribution to household income, improvement in consumption level, savings, enhancement of self-confidence, contribution to food security and health care contribution since the respective „F“ statistics are significant at 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Impact of women self help group on the living condition and the education of respondents

To find out the significant difference in the impact of women's self-help groups on the living conditions among the rural poor of different education, ANOVA was attempted with the null hypothesis as **there is no significant difference in the impact of women's self-help group on the living condition among the different education of rural poor in Tirunelveli district**. The resulting mean score among the rural poor of different education on the status and the respective „F“ statistics are presented in Table 3.

Table - 3

Impact of women self help group on the living condition and the education of respondents in Tirunelveli district

Sl. No	Impact of women self help group on the living condition	Education (Mean Score among the Respondents)				F Statistics
		Illiterate	Primary	Middle School	High School	
1.	Sustainable changes in own lives	3.1905	3.3627	3.1892	3.3750	0.560
2.	Improvement in consumption level	3.3810	3.3109	3.1081	3.2917	0.457
3.	Savings	3.3333	3.3834	3.1892	3.3145	0.329
4.	Enhancement of self-confidence	3.6190	3.1917	3.0270	3.3333	0.998
5.	Contribution to food security	3.3249	2.9896	2.9189	2.8750	0.951
6.	Health care contribution	3.2381	3.0260	3.0541	2.9167	0.419
7.	Repayment of debts	3.0000	3.0541	3.1545	3.1457	0.167
8.	Contribution to their family expenditure	3.4286	3.4093	3.5405	3.8333	1.580
9.	Participation in income generation	3.2381	3.2280	3.0270	3.2083	0.510
10.	Decision-making skills	3.2852	3.3990	3.1351	3.2917	0.698
11.	Economic independence	2.9048	3.3420	3.2432	3.0000	1.553
12.	Earning opportunities	2.9524	3.4093	3.3243	2.9500	2.506*
13.	Contribution to household income	2.9025	3.2487	3.2973	3.1000	1.491

Source: Primary data

*Significant at five per cent level

Table 3 shows the mean score of the impact of women's self-help groups on the living conditions among different education of rural poor along with its respective „F“ statistics. The important impact of women's self-help groups on the living conditions among the rural poor who are illiterates are enhancement of self-confidence and contribution to their family and their respective mean scores are 3.4286 and 3.6190 among the rural poor who have primary educational qualifications, earning opportunities, and contribution to their family expenditure, and their respective mean scores are 3.4093. and 3.5337. The important impact of the women's self-help group on the living condition among the rural poor who are middle school qualifications are a contribution to their family expenditure and earning opportunities and their respective mean scores are 3.3243 and 3.5405, among the rural poor who are high school educational qualification, sustainable changes in own lives and contribute to their family expenditure and their respective mean scores are 3.3750 and 3.8333. Regarding the impact of women's self-help groups on the living condition, the significant difference among the different education of rural poor, are identified in the case of earning opportunities since the respective „F“ statistics is significant at a 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Problems in women self help group and the age group of rural poor

To find out the significant difference in the problems in women's self-help GROUP among different age groups of rural poor in Tirunelveli district, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was attempted with the null hypothesis as “There is no significant difference in the problems in women self-help group among different age groups of rural poor in Tirunelveli district”. The resulting mean score among different age groups of rural poor on the problems in the women's self-help group and the respective „F“ statistics are presented in Table 4.

Table - 4

Problems in women self help group and Age group of rural poor- ANOVA

Sl. No	Problems in women self help group	Age Group (Mean Score)				F Statistics
		Less than 25 years	26-35 years	36-45 years	Above 46 years	
1.	Lack of crèche facility for	3.2211	3.3324	3.2320	3.4135	2.133

	children					
2.	Lack of shading tents during rest period	3.3654	3.5056	3.3944	3.5193	1.747
3.	Ex-gratia payment for injury cases	3.2140	3.4648	3.4435	3.4904	4.205*
4.	Toiletry facilities	3.1073	3.2986	3.2807	3.4808	3.209*
5.	No extra facilities are given to women	3.0807	3.2366	3.1638	3.3077	1.179
6	Lack of safe drinking water	3.0395	3.2056	3.1614	3.3654	2.149
7	Delayed response	3.3652	3.5140	3.4548	3.5962	2.696*
8.	Bribe	3.6049	3.8006	3.6441	3.8462	4.904*
9.	Unpleasant attitude	3.5769	3.7768	3.7360	3.8077	3.374*
10.	Non-availability of first aid facility	3.5763	3.7725	3.6299	4.0000	2.532*
11.	Work place distance	3.6667	3.8112	3.7416	3.9327	2.637*
12.	Misuse of job card by the others	3.4394	3.5791	3.5790	3.6154	1.072

Source: Computed Data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

Table 4 shows the mean score of problems in the women's self-help group among the different age groups of rural poor along with its respective „F“ statistics. The important problems in the women's self-help group among the rural poor who are in the age group of fewer than 25 years are workplace distance and bribes and their respective mean scores are 3.6667 and 3.6049. Among the rural poor who are in the age group of 26 to 35 years, the important problems in the women's self-help group are workplace distance and unpleasant attitude and their respective mean scores are 3.7416 and 3.7360. The important problems in the women's self-help group among the rural poor who are in the age group of 36-45 years are workplace distance and bribes and their respective mean scores are 3.8112 and 3.8006. Among the rural poor who are in the age group above 46 years, the important problems in the women's self-help group are the non-availability of first aid facilities and workplace distance and their respective mean scores are

4.0000 and 3.9327. Regarding the problems in the women's self-help group, the significant differences among the different age groups of rural poor, are identified in the case of delayed response, bribes, unpleasant attitude, non-availability of first aid facility, workplace distance, payment for injury cases, and toiletry facilities, since the respective „F“ statistics are significant at 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Problems in women's self-help groups among the different marital statuses of rural poor

To find out the significant difference in the problems in women self-help groups among the different marital statuses of rural poor in Tirunelveli district, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was attempted with the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in the problems in women self-help group among the different marital status of rural poor in Tirunelveli district”. The resulting mean score among the different marital statuses of rural poor on the problems in the women self-help group and the respective „F“ statistics are presented in Table 5.

Table - 5

Problems in women self-help group among the different marital status of rural poor- ANOVA

Sl. No	Problems in women self help group	Marital Status (Mean Score)			F Statistics
		Married	Unmarried	Widow	
1.	Lack of creche facility for children	3.1026	3.0514	3.3668	7.347*
2.	Lack of shading tents during rest period	3.4679	3.4263	3.5256	0.461
3.	Ex-gratia payment for injury cases	3.4169	3.3623	3.6026	2.079
4.	Toiletry facilities	3.3636	3.2495	3.7564	5.412*
5.	No extra facilities are given to women	3.3856	3.1794	3.5385	3.415*
6.	Lack of safe drinking water	3.2759	3.1557	3.4487	4.260*
7.	Delayed response	3.5688	3.3738	3.7089	6.539*

8..	Bribe	3.7844	3.6377	3.9620	5.078*
9.	Unpleasant attitude	3.7250	3.7033	3.7722	0.247
10.	Non-availability of first aid facility	3.8156	3.6120	3.9747	3.441*
11..	Work place distance	3.7563	3.7118	4.1139	6.514*
12.	Misuse of job card by the others	3.5078	3.4993	3.8861	3.784*

Source: Computed Data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

Table 5 shows the mean score of problems in the women's self-help group among the different marital statuses of the rural poor along with their respective „F“ statistics. The important problems in the women's self-help group among the rural poor who are married are the non-availability of first aid facilities and bribe and their respective mean scores are 3.8156 and 3.7844. The important problems in the women's self-help group among the rural poor who are unmarried are workplace distance and unpleasant attitude and their respective mean scores are 3.7118 and 3.7033. Among the rural poor who are widows the important problems in women's workplace distance and non-availability of first aid facility and their respective mean scores are 4.1139 and 3.9747. Regarding the problems in a women's self-help group, the significant differences among the different marital statuses of rural poor, are identified in the case of delayed response, bribes, non-availability of first aid facility, workplace distance, misuse of job cards by others, lack of creche facility for children, toiletry facilities, no extra facilities are given to women and lack of safe drinking water, since the respective „F“ statistics are significant at 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected.

SUGGESTIONS

Respondents are not satisfied with the number of working days provided through the women's self-help group. So the Government tries to raise the number of working days of the scheme. The government tries to increase the wage provided under the women's self-help group because respondents are dissatisfied with the present wage. The present income level of the women self-help group beneficiary is not increased after joining this scheme. The government

tries to increase the income level for the women self-help group beneficiaries. Need to improve the working conditions of the Scheme.

- It is suggested that there should be separate cells created for the women workers to ensure their effective participation in the women's self-help group scheme.
- It is also suggested that there should not be a delay in payment of the wages under this scheme because it can affect their day-to-day activities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the evaluation carried out at the field level, it can be inferred that women's self-help group holds the key to the development of the country's vast rural population. The program is deemed to have huge potential in empowering rural communities. The program is capable of enhancing the income level, food security, and livelihood security of the rural poor sustainably. Women's self-help groups brought very positive changes in respect of employment, income, wage rates, and food security. It boosted the village economy and was found beneficial to the rural poor.

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